

The Link Between Real Wave Quantum Mechanics and the Time-Independent Schrödinger Equation

Ron Ewins

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Abstract

This note explores the relationship between Real Wave Quantum Mechanics (RWQM) and conventional Quantum Mechanics (QM) as described by the Schrödinger equation. It has been shown previously [Ewins(2021)] that RWQM and QM give identical results for various 1-D well potentials, providing the FRs making up the Eigenstructures have phases alternating by π radians. The reason why this leads to congruence with the Schrödinger equation is examined qualitatively, and is confirmed quantitatively for cosine solution forms.

1 Introduction

It has been shown in a previous paper [Ewins(2021)] that Real Wave Quantum Mechanics (RWQM) can give the same results as the Schrödinger equation for 1-dimensional potential wells. Figures 1 and 2 compare results obtained by a normal application of Schrödinger's equation [Polson(2021)] calculated using the matrix method for a Simple Harmonic Oscillator (SHO) potential well, compared with the results obtained from RWQM. (Parameters used in the RWQM calculation were adjusted to enable a good comparison to be made.)

Figure 2 masks an important feature of the RWQM results, namely that the phase at successive Field Rotators (FRs) alternates by π radians. This was initially surprising, but further work has shown that it is inevitable. In fact it is *why* RWQM leads to the same results as the Schrödinger equation. This is explored in the current paper with partial success - the method used works for regions where ψ has a sinusoidal envelope but is not satisfactory for regions of exponential decay.

Figure 1: SHO potential. Results for $N = 2000$ and $V(y) = 10^5 (y - 1/2)^2$

Figure 2: SHO potential. RWQM results for ψ^2 . Compare with Figure 1

2 Qualitative Considerations

2.1 Restrictions Arising from the 1 Dimensional case

A 1-dimensional treatment of RWQM is extremely restrictive. FRs are descriptive of rotation which requires 2-dimensions. In fact, later work [Ewins(2022)] has indicated the three dimensional nature of structures. In 1D, a structure is simply a list of complex numbers (each associated with a discrete point along a line), which encode the magnitude and phase of the FR located there. Because the FRs are along a line and are separated by one wavelength, arriving waves have the same phase as the FR generating them. The process of adding and discriminating the phase vectors of arriving waves applicable to higher dimensions

reduces to simple summation of the arriving amplitudes i.e.:

$$F_R(\psi_i) = \alpha \left[\sum_{n=-\infty}^{i-1} \frac{-\psi_n}{n} + \sum_{n=i+1}^{\infty} \frac{\psi_n}{n} \right]$$

Here, F_R is an operator which, when applied to the i th FR, returns the summed contribution from all the other FRs in the structure. The magnitude of each contribution falls inversely as the distance from its source. (Note that in the non-physical case that ψ_n was constant, it could be factored out and what remained would be the sum of two non-converging harmonic series.)

Mathematically, the steady state equation for RWQM can be written ¹:

$$\psi_i = (F_R\psi_i + \psi_i) g_i$$

In words, given the steady state values of ψ at each of the i points, if we operate on them with F_R to obtain the contributions from every other FR and add these contributions to the ψ_i 's, and then multiply by the local gain function, g_i , we get back to where we started.

2.2 The Reason for Phase Alternation

Phase alternation was identified by the application of the RWQM matrix method. However, the reason for it is apparent. If all the FRs were in phase, then the summed contributions at every FR must be positive. Because FRs always have gains from the vacuum (i.e. we expect g_i to be greater than 1), it would not be possible to generate stable structures. It follows that at least some FRs must have opposite phase (intermediate phases are not considered in the 1-D case). But opposite phases cannot be distributed 'at random' because the negatives and positives must have a balanced relationship for every FR. Alternating opposite phases are inevitable. Alternating phases also convert the harmonic series identified in the F_R operator expression to the alternating harmonic series, which conditionally converges to $\ln 2$.

An important consequence of alternating phases is that the summed contributions to one FR from all the others is always out of phase (i.e. of opposite sign). This is because the FRs adjacent to the FR in question always have opposite phase and as they are the leading terms of the series they indicate the convergence sign (i.e. $\approx \pm \ln 2$). As will be shown in the next Section, it is this feature which leads to congruence with the Schrödinger equation.

2.3 Qualitative Intuition

RWQM leads to alternating FR phases, but why does this lead to congruence with the Schrödinger equation? Figure 3 provides some intuition. In the left

¹A subtlety arises because the matrix method actually applies:

$$\psi_i = F_R\psi_i + \psi_i g_i$$

The gain is applied to the original ψ magnitude before the contribution is added which gives a slightly different value for eigenvalues than the expression above.

Figure 3: Curvature Resulting From Phase Alternation

hand diagram three points are envisaged where the amount of gain g_{crit} exactly balances the scattering losses. The points a, b and c are essentially equivalent and must fall along a straight line. In the central diagram we consider two points d and f existing in a region where the gain is greater than g_{crit} . For the FR at e to be in a steady state it must therefore be receiving an additional negative (out of phase) contribution. This will arise if the FRs at d and f (the leading terms in the series) have higher $|\psi|$ values than in the critical case. This corresponds to a curvature away from the axis, such as would be expected in the inverse exponential zones of the solutions to Schrödinger's equation. On the other hand, the right hand diagram depicts the situation where $g < g_{crit}$. The FR at h would not be receiving sufficient gain to cover its losses if the three FRs were in a straight line, so the FRs at g and i must have lower $|\psi|$ values (less negative contribution). This corresponds to downward curvature, such as would be expected in the sinusoidal zones of the solutions to Schrödinger's equation.

What does it mean when the Schrödinger equation gives negative values for the amplitudes? Since RWQM already has alternating phases, the negative Schrödinger amplitudes indicate that the order of phases has changed at the $\psi = 0$ axis (e.g. $+, -, +, -, -, +, -$). ψ vanishes on the axis because each FR above it is matched by one of opposite phase below it.

3 Quantitative Results

The author has not been able to show with mathematical rigour that RWQM leads to Schrödinger's equation but given the level of agreement between Figures 1 and 2 it seems a reasonable postulate. Some weight can be added by considering regions within a particular eigenstructure which follow a sinusoidal pattern, for example, in the central region of a finite square well. Figure 4 shows such a result, taken from [Ewins(2021)]. The central green curve has constant potential and is sinusoidal.

The method employed is as follows:

- assign a phase to a particular FR
- for each value of the gain:

Figure 4: First four Finite Square Well ψ^2 , Well width = 500, Wall height = $3e - 7$, $\alpha = 1/137$

- postulate a sinusoidal form having a wave vector k and use this to calculate the ψ values for all FRs other than the one selected.
- calculate the resulting ψ at the selected FR using $\psi_i = (F_R\psi_i + \psi_i)g_i$
- compare this with the correct result for a ψ envelope with this k value
- adjust k using an optimizing algorithm until the ψ 's calculated in the two ways are in agreement.
- check other initial FRs to ensure that the relationship between k and g is independent of position in the wave.

This has been done using n values ± 1000 units either side of the selected FR and the results are shown in Figure 5 as a plot of k^2 against g . It shows that the relationship between g and k^2 is linear, and that there is indeed a value of g_{crit} for which k is zero. This relationship proves to be independent of the initial phase at the selected FR, as required.

Figure 6 replots the results in terms of k and $\sqrt{g_{crit} - g}$ showing the direct relationship more clearly. This can be compared with the QM result for zones of constant potential:

$$\psi \propto \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{2mE}}{\hbar}x\right)$$

Figure 5: k^2 vs g Alternating cosine with n in range ± 1000 and $\alpha = 1/137$

Figure 6: k vs $\sqrt{g_{crit} - g}$ Alternating cosine with n in range ± 1000 and $\alpha = 1/137$

Here,

$$k \equiv \frac{\sqrt{2mE}}{\hbar}, E \equiv g_{crit-g}$$

so RWQM gives the same form of result as QM.

Unfortunately, it is not possible to apply the same methodology in the the inverse exponential zones because if they are left unbounded (i.e. not meshing in with a sinusoidal zone) the exponential terms overpower the alternating harmonic terms in the direction of increasing ψ .

4 Conclusions

There are huge differences between the interpretations of QM and RWQM. The former deals with the probabilistic attributes of hypothetical point particles and leads to many difficulties such as intrinsic spin angular momentum, whereas the latter describes extended structures having 'normal' angular momentum. However, for this simple 1-D case the interpretations agree on the mathematical form of the 'wave function' which is described by the Schrödinger equation. For QM the square of its absolute value represents a probability density cloud. For RWQM it represents the 'mass' density (albeit being located at discrete FR locations). What mass *is* in this context perhaps needs some clarification. The basic assumption for RWQM is an underlying longitudinal wave bearing medium. This is assumed to have a mass attribute of some sort. However, it only becomes locally observable particle mass when it is 'locked' into permanent rotation within a stable structure having a distinct location. The mass associated with the wave medium might be otherwise observable on cosmic scales.

References

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